

UTILIZATION OF GROUNDNUT MEAL

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Groundnut meal has been assayed; the nitrogenous matter as present in the nuts has been extracted by different processes and the proteinous body of the meal has been subjected to the digestive action of various enzymes.

It was previously observed (Basu and Ganguly, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.* 1944, Part III, p. 48) that a flour rich in protein, mineral and vitamin contents and suitable for human consumption may be prepared from groundnut meal. Groundnut oil has been removed from groundnut by mechanical press and the meal left behind is used either as a fodder or a fertilizer. Certain characteristics of this meal are now being compared with one that has been obtained in this laboratory by drying the decorticated groundnuts, removing the pericarp and finally extracting out the oil from the powdered groundnut meal by means of petroleum ether (b. p. 50-60°). It may be mentioned here that as groundnuts are being largely produced in India, any knowledge that may be gathered on the development of a method of extracting the oil and thereby, getting a better type of meal, would go a long way for the improvement of groundnut oil industry in the country. The residual meal may be properly utilized not only as food, but also in the production of adhesives, plastics, water-paints and allied materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydraulic-pressed cake, as kindly supplied by Messrs. Swaika Oil Mills, Calcutta, was used in this investigation. This was finely powdered in a mill (60 mesh), and was then stored at room temperature (30°) in large glass-stoppered bottles previously cleaned and dried at 150°. This and the solvent-extracted meal were analysed and the results are being recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Substance	Comparative analysis of pressed meal and solvent-extracted meal.						
	Moisture	Ash	Ether extract	Protein	Fibre	Carbohydrate	Nicotinic acid (mg / 100 g.)
Pressed meal	8.1%	5.75%	5.43%	52.93%	5.71%	22.08%	.28
Solvent-extracted meal	6.05	5.1	8.82	49	6.2	24.83	25

Each of the above meals was assayed for its nitrogen content and then extracted under different conditions. It may be recorded here that 90 to 95% of the nitrogen in groundnut meal is present as protein nitrogen (*cf.* Higgins *et al.*, *Agr. Expt. Sta. Bull.*, 1941, No. 213, p. 3). The amount of nitrogenous substances extracted by the process, described below, was determined by finding out the nitrogen per cent in the extract by the macro-Kjeldahl method on aliquots of the clear centrifugates. The total amount of nitrogen in the solvent added was then calculated out. From this the percentages of total nitrogen extracted out from the cake in question were found out and are recorded in Tables II and III. Usually 2.5 g. of the powdered meal were taken for extraction with about 100 c.c. of different solvents, and were kept for one hour at the room temperature with occasional shaking. After the period, the whole was centrifuged and an aliquot part of the supernatant liquid was taken for estimation.

The solvent extracted meal was then subjected to enzymatic digestion by papain (Ceylon variety) at p_H 5.5 (A); papain after activation with sulphuretted hydrogen according to the method of Frankel *et al.* (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 1926) (B); by trypsin at p_H 8.1 (C); by trypsin in presence of 15% alcohol (D); by pepsin (B. D. H.) at p_H 1.8 (F), and directly by hydrochloric acid (20 per cent) under reflux for 18 hours (E), to see what percentages of nitrogenous matter as present in the meal, might undergo a peptization under varying condi-

tions. For this, 10 g. of the meal were at first suspended in 100 c.c. of water in presence of the respective enzymes at 50°. In case of papain 2.5 g. of the enzyme were used for each experiment (20 c.c.); whereas in case of pepsin only 1 g. of the enzyme was used. From the suspension 10 c.c. of the supernatant liquid were taken, treated with 5 c.c. of trichloroacetic acid (5%) to free it from any protein and the filtrate was assayed for finding out the soluble nitrogen by the usual Kjeldahl method. Similar experiments were carried out in presence of each enzyme after digesting the mass for a period of 24 and 96 hours. From these, the amount of the meal that has undergone peptization was found out as above, after trichloroacetic acid treatment, and the respective data under varying conditions as obtained from an average of three experiments are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE II

Pressed meal containing 8.47% N.

Expt.	Extraction solvent	p_H of pension	% of total meal N extracted
1	NaOH (4%)	10	85.3
2	"	8.5	69.5
3	NaOH and NaCl (6%)	"	55
4	"	7.5	56
5	Dilute NH ₃ (1:1)	8.5	65.2
6	Dilute NH ₃ and NaCl (6%)	8.5	65

TABLE III

Solvent-extracted meal containing 7.84% N.

Expt.	Extraction solvent	p_H of pension	% of total meal N extracted
1	NaOH (4%)	10	88.3
2	"	8.5	75.2
3	NaOH and NaCl (6%)	"	77
4	"	7.5	60
5	Dilute NH ₃ (1:1)	8.5	72
6	"	7.5	70.5
7	Dilute NH ₃ and NaCl (6%)	8.5	74.8

TABLE IV

Solvent-extracted meal containing 7.84% N.

Expts.	Total meal N undergoing peptization		
	0 hour	24 hours	96 hours
'A'	20%	54%	56%
'B'	22	60	64
'C'	25	60.5	70
'D'	20	71.3	82.5
'E'	20	62.8	74.5
'F'	...	100*	...
		* in 18 hours	

From Table I, it may be noticed that chemically the pressed meal does not appreciably vary from the solvent-extracted one. But while extracting out the nitrogenous matter from the respective meals it has always been noticed (*vide* Tables II and III) that solvent-extracted meal always gave a larger yield of nitrogenous matter in the extract. This shows that most probably under the high pressure of the hydraulic press which is usually used in extracting the oil from groundnut, the nitrogenous body as present in groundnut has undergone some changes that lower down its solubility in the various solvents that have been employed throughout the course of this investigation. This characteristic change in the protein molecule of groundnut in the pressed cake is also being noticed in connection with other experiments which are also in progress in this laboratory. It is always being noticed by us that the nitrogenous constituents are better extracted at p_H higher than 8.5. Fontaine and Burnett (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1944, 36, 164) have noticed that more than 90 per cent of the nitrogenous constituents can be peptized at p_H 7.2 or above if the meal be allowed to stand for 3 hours at room temperature (25°). From the data in Table IV it would be evident that the proteinous nitrogen as present in the meal (solvent-extracted) has undergone a proteolytic cleavage under the influence of all the common proteolytic enzymes. In this respect trypsin in presence of alcohol (Experiment D) is most effective. More than 82% of the nitrogenous body as was present in the meal could be recovered by the latter process.

Further work on the characteristics of the protein as present in the groundnut as well as on the nature of their fragmented molecules after enzymatic digestions is in progress. It is also being contemplated to find out the difference, if any, in the characteristics of the proteinous body that might be extracted out from the groundnut by the different solvents.